

About Fractional Programming Problems and *SIR* Models

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Abstract:

Fractional programming problems have attracted the attention of many specialists due to their applications in many fields as Economics and Finance, Engineering, Biology, Epidemiology, Medicine, etc. In this article, we present examples of the problems of the fractional programming, and we discussed a parallel between the *SIR* models built using classical differential equations and using fractional differential equations. Epidemiological models (i.e. *SIR* model and its generalizations) or pollution models, can provide

particular cases of numerators and denominators for objective functions in fractional programming problems. For the *SIR* epidemiological model, the article discusses the existence of the solution for its generalization and brings a novelty regarding its approach as a model with partial derivatives. In the classical models, the rate of change is more abrupt, which suggests a more deterministic and predictable behavior in the spread of the disease. The fractional derivative brings a memory effect, which makes the spread and recovery slower and more extended over time. Simulations of many optimization problems were also realized in GeoGebra, Maple and MATLAB software. A case study related to optimizing vaccination rates between two regions, applied the Frank-Wolfe method for a fractional programming problem and an implementation in Maple. In the case study, in a context of a city divided into two regions, we supposed that the authorities aim to optimize the vaccination rate to minimize the combined infection rate. The aim was to maximize the ratio between vaccination effectiveness and total costs. A principal conclusion is that the use of simulations, for example, in GeoGebra, Maple or MATLAB software, can increase the quality of the teaching-learning process for students, in subjects such as Operational Research or Optimization Techniques.

Keywords: *Fractional Programming, Simulations, Optimization.*

Introduction

In the contemporary mathematics, fractional programming problems have attracted the attention of many specialists due to their applications in the real world (Economics and Finance: optimization of economic indices, portfolio optimization, cost-benefit analysis, sales or profits, production planning for costs; Engineering: design optimization, resource allocation in telecommunication networks,

performance evaluation in manufacturing systems, engineering for inventory or for signal processing, statistics, physics; Operations Research: Efficiency analysis in production processes, transportation, logistics planning; Biology and medicine: statistics, etc.) (Dinkelbach, 1967; Sadeghi et al., 2019; Salahi, 2009).

Fractional programming problems are called ratio optimization problems or fractional optimization problems in the specialized

literature. One of the earliest examples of this was introduced in 1937 by von Neumann and is an equilibrium model for an expanding economy. The model determines the growth rate of an economy as the maximum of the smallest of the output-input ratios. But, the systematic study of fractional programming started much later.

Thus, fractional programming is a branch of mathematical optimization that deals with problems involving the optimization of ratios of functions. These problems arise naturally in various fields such as economics, finance, engineering, and operations research. The primary goal in fractional programming is to maximize or minimize a ratio of functions, which can represent efficiency, productivity, or other performance metrics.

The classical form of fractional programming problems is:

$$\begin{cases} \max \frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \\ x \in M \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where M is a subset of the linear space R^n , $f: M \rightarrow R_+$, $g: M \rightarrow R_+$. (Neculai, 2003)

In 1962, Charnes and Cooper published their paper in which they showed that a linear fractional program with a ratio can be reduced to a linear program using a nonlinear variable transformation.

Charnes and Cooper reformulated problem (1), introducing the following notations $z = \frac{1}{g(x)}$ and $q = \frac{x}{g(x)}$, and thus rewrote the problem in the form (2):

$$\begin{cases} \max z f \left(\frac{q}{z} \right) \\ z g \left(\frac{q}{z} \right) \leq 1 \\ x \in M \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Martos in showed that linear fractional problems can be solved with a vertex traversal procedure just like linear programming problems.

The study of single-ratio fractional optimization problems has largely dominated specialized literature until around 1980.

Many of the then known results were presented in the first monograph on fractional programming (Schaible, 1978). Since then other monographs dedicated exclusively to fractional programming have appeared, in 1988 (Craven), in 1997 (Stancu-Minasian), in 1998 (Barros), etc.

Fractional programs with one or more ratios have often been studied in the broader context of generalized convex programming (Avriel et al., 1988; Martos, 1975; Pramy et.al., 2017, Schaible, 1995; etc.).

Fractional programming also overlaps with global optimization. Many types of ratio optimization problems have local, not global, optimal points.

Wolf (1985) gave a solution method for fractional linear programming. For fractional quadratic programming, solution methods are found in Rajendra (1993), Seshan and Tibekar (1980), Chandra and Chandramoham (1980), etc. And for the case of fractional quadratic programming, Swarup (1965) provided an algorithm for determining the solution. The case where the constraints are linear and the objective function is the quotient of a convex function with a concave function was solved by Mangasarian (1969) using the Frank and Wolfe (1956) algorithm.(Jeflea, 2003)

In an article from 2019, Sadeghi and the coauthors considered a fractional program with linear and quadratic expressions, in numerator and denominator and used second order cone constraints. With a change of variable, the authors transformed the program into a second order cone programming problem.

The nonlinear fractional programming problem also arises in various decision-making situations. There are different algorithms for determining the solution, such as gradient methods (Prangprakhon et al., 2022) or algorithms for solving nonlinear fractional programming based

on the parametric approach to the fractional programming problem given by Dinkelbach (1967). An example of this is given in Gopal et al. (1991) which investigates the optimal design management of logical networks.

Dinkelbach reformulated problem (1) in the form (3):

$$\begin{cases} \max[f(x) - yg(x)] \\ x \in M \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where the auxiliary variable y was iteratively defined as follows:

$$y(t+1) = \frac{f(x(t))}{g(x(t))} \quad (4)$$

Others results, of Farkas-type, for a fractional programming problem, is due to Sun et Al. (2018). These authors used the dualizing function, the Lagrangian function, the epigraph of the conjugate functions.

Some description of robust optimal solutions for uncertain fractional optimization and some applications is due to Sun and the coauthors (2017).

Thus, in the present optimization theory, the major types of fractional programming include:

- Linear Fractional Programming (LFP): Both the numerator and denominator are linear functions. This is the most well-studied type, with applications in decision-making and resource allocation;

-Nonlinear Fractional Programming (NFP): Involves nonlinear functions, making the problems more complex and challenging to solve. These problems often arise in engineering design and economic modeling;

-Multi-objective Fractional Programming (MOFP): Deals with multiple ratios that need to be optimized simultaneously. This is relevant in scenarios where trade-offs between different performance measures must be evaluated.

In the contemporary mathematics, some of the notable techniques to solve fractional programming problems, include:

-Charnes-Cooper Transformation: A method to convert a fractional problem into a linear one, applicable mainly to linear fractional programming;

-Dinkelbach's Algorithm: An iterative algorithm that solves a series of simpler problems to converge to the optimal solution of a fractional programming problem;

-Branch and Bound Methods: Used for solving mixed-integer and nonlinear fractional programming problems by systematically exploring feasible solutions;

-Convex Optimization Approaches: Leveraging the properties of convex functions to find global optima in certain classes of nonlinear fractional programming problems.

Recent research in fractional programming has focused on expanding the applicability and efficiency of solution techniques. Advances in computational power and algorithmic design have enabled the handling of larger and more complex problems. Some notable trends include:

-Metaheuristic Algorithms: Techniques such as genetic algorithms, simulated annealing, and particle swarm optimization have been employed to tackle complex nonlinear fractional problems;

-Robust and Stochastic Fractional Programming: Addressing uncertainties and variability in model parameters to provide more resilient solutions;

-Multi-criteria Decision Making (MCDM): Integrating fractional programming with MCDM techniques to handle problems involving multiple conflicting objectives.

This article is organized as follows. In Section 1, "Introduction", some elements from the literature review. Section 2 "Mathematical modeling", contains a set of theorems from the specialty literature about the methods for solve fractional programming problems. Section 3, "Main Results" contains details about the SIR model and its generalizations, its components being

numerators and denominators of objective functions for fractional programming problems. We also included comparisons between the results given by the classical and fractional epidemiological models. Also, calculation examples for equilibrium points, solution existence conditions, stability analysis, for epidemiological models. In section 4, "Simulations", simulations in four informatics programs and a case study and numerical example- an application of the Frank-Wolfe method. In section 5, the conclusions of the article.

Examples of Most Significant Theorems

Fractional programming encompasses several key theorems that provide a theoretical foundation for solving these optimization problems. Here are some of the most significant theorems:

Theorem 1. (Charnes & Cooper, 1962) *Consider the fractional programming problem:*

$$\begin{cases} \max \left(\frac{c^T x}{d^T x} \right) \\ Ax \leq b \\ d^T x > 0 \\ x \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

by introducing a new variable $t = \frac{1}{d^T x}$, and defining $y = tx$, the problem can be transformed into the following linear programming problem:

$$\begin{cases} \max(c^T y) \\ Ay \leq bt \\ d^T y = 1 \\ y, t \geq 0 \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

This transformation ensures that the optimal solution of the linear programming problem corresponds to the optimal solution of the original fractional programming problem.

Dinkelbach's algorithm provides a method for solving nonlinear fractional programming problems.

Theorem 2. (Dinkelbach's Algorithm Theorem, 1967) *Consider the nonlinear fractional programming problem:*

$$\begin{cases} \max \left(\frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right) \\ g(x) > 0 \\ x \in S \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Define the auxiliary function: $\phi(x, \lambda) = f(x) - \lambda g(x)$. For a given λ , solve the following problem iteratively: $\max \phi(x, \lambda)$, subject to: $x \in S$. If $\phi(x^*, \lambda) = 0$, where x^* the optimal solution, then x^* is also the optimal solution to the original problem.

The algorithm proceeds by updating λ as: $\lambda_{k+1} = \frac{f(x_k)}{g(x_k)}$. This process is repeated until convergence.

Theorem 3. (Geometric Programming Theorem) (Gomory, 1967)

Given a problem of the form:

$$\begin{cases} \min \frac{c_1 x_1^{a_{11}} x_2^{a_{12}} \dots x_n^{a_{1n}} + \dots + c_k x_1^{a_{k1}} x_2^{a_{k2}} \dots x_n^{a_{kn}}}{d_1 x_1^{b_{11}} x_2^{b_{12}} \dots x_n^{b_{1n}} + \dots + d_m x_1^{b_{m1}} x_2^{b_{m2}} \dots x_n^{b_{mn}}} \\ x_i > 0, i = \overline{1, n} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

This problem can be reformulated and solved using the properties of geometric programming.

Duality principles in linear programming can be extended to linear fractional programming.

Theorem 4. (Duality Theorem for Linear Fractional Programming) (Schaible, 1995) *For the primal linear fractional programming problem:*

$$\begin{cases} \max \left(\frac{c^T x + \alpha}{d^T x + \beta} \right) \\ Ax \leq b \\ x \geq 0 \\ \alpha, \beta \in R \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

the corresponding dual problem can be formulated, and strong duality holds, meaning that the optimal value of the primal problem is equal to the optimal value of the dual problem.

These theorems provide a robust theoretical framework for understanding and solving fractional programming problems, facilitating their application in various fields.

Main Results

The functions f and g in formula (1) can be the number of infected plus the number of susceptible, relative to the number of exposed plus the number of recovered from an epidemiological model. Or, $S, I, R,$ can be compartments in a pollution mathematical model (susceptible soil area $S(t)$, the surface affected by industrial pollution $I(t)$, the soil with action taken by applying some necessary remedies $R(t)$) (Priya & Sabarmathi, 2022). Such a model is the following and represents a generalization of the SIR model and of the $SEIR$ model is of the form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{dI(t)}{dt} &= \sigma E(t) - cI(t) - \mu I(t) \\
 +k_1(t)N(t) - k_2(t)N(t) + k_3(t)N(t) - k_4(t)N(t) \\
 \frac{dE(t)}{dt} &= \beta S(t) \frac{I(t)}{N(t)} - \sigma E(t) - \nu E(t) \\
 +k_1(t)N(t) - k_2(t)N(t) + k_3(t)N(t) - k_4(t)N(t) \\
 \frac{dN(t)}{dt} &= \mu N(t) - \nu N(t) + k_1(t)N(t) \\
 -k_2(t)N(t) + k_3(t)N(t) - k_4(t)N(t) \\
 \frac{dR(t)}{dt} &= cI(t) - \nu R(t) + k_1(t)N(t) \\
 -k_2(t)N(t) + k_3(t)N(t) - k_4(t)N(t) \\
 \frac{dS(t)}{dt} &= \mu N(t) - \nu S(t) - \beta S(t) \frac{I(t)}{N(t)} \\
 +k_1(t)N(t) - k_2(t)N(t) + k_3(t)N(t) - k_4(t)N(t)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{11}$$

where $k_i, i = 1 \dots 4$ are coefficients of immigration, emigration, influencing factor of the pollution in the analyzed area, and indicator of the quality level of healthcare services. t is the time variable and $\sigma, c, \mu, \beta, \nu$ are other parameters of the model. The derivatives in the left members of the system (11) can be replaced by

fractional derivatives to obtain a more refined model. (Bucur, 2022)

To make a simulation of this epidemiological model (11), we will implement the system of differential equations using the Euler method, using initial conditions and generic values for the parameters. The model is an extended SIR (Susceptible, Infected, Recovered) type system with a component for exposed (E) and an additional term $N(t)$ affecting each equation (this quantifies the volume of the statistical population at time t).

The generic parameters for the simulation are:

- $\sigma, c, \mu, \nu, \beta$: transition and infection rates.
- $k_1(t), k_2(t), k_3(t), k_4(t)$: temporal functions affecting the population $N(t)$.

Initial conditions of the model (11) are:

- $S(0), E(0), I(0), R(0), N(0)$: initial values for the respective populations.

And the implementation steps for simulating the epidemiological model (11) using the Euler method are as follows:

1. The required libraries are imported: numpy for numerical operations and matplotlib.pyplot for data visualization.
2. The parameters of the model are defined: transition rates, infection, mortality, etc.
3. Initial conditions: set the initial values for each compartment in the model.
4. Time simulation: Define the time interval and time step for the simulation.
5. The variables for each compartment are initialized.
6. The dynamics are simulated using the Euler method: the values are iteratively updated using the differential equations in the model (11).
7. Plotting the results: Use matplotlib to display the results.

The Python code for the simulation is as follows:

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

```

# The generic parameters
sigma = 0.5
c = 0.3
mu = 0.01
nu = 0.02
beta = 0.4

# Functions k(t)
def k1(t): return 0.05 * np.sin(0.1 * t)
def k2(t): return 0.03 * np.sin(0.2 * t)
def k3(t): return 0.04 * np.sin(0.3 * t)
def k4(t): return 0.02 * np.sin(0.4 * t)

# Variables initialization
S = np.zeros(len(t))
E = np.zeros(len(t))
I = np.zeros(len(t))
R = np.zeros(len(t))
N = np.zeros(len(t))

# Setting initial conditions
S[0] = S0
E[0] = E0
I[0] = I0
R[0] = R0
N[0] = N0

# Numerical simulation using the Euler method
for i in range(1, len(t)):
    k1_t = k1(t[i-1])
    k2_t = k2(t[i-1])
    k3_t = k3(t[i-1])
    k4_t = k4(t[i-1])

    dI_dt = sigma * E[i-1] - c * I[i-1] - mu * I[i-1]
    + (k1_t - k2_t + k3_t - k4_t) * N[i-1]
    dE_dt = beta * S[i-1] * I[i-1] / N[i-1] - sigma
    * E[i-1] - nu * E[i-1] + (k1_t - k2_t + k3_t - k4_t)
    * N[i-1]
    dN_dt = mu * N[i-1] - nu * N[i-1] + (k1_t -
    k2_t + k3_t - k4_t) * N[i-1]
    dR_dt = c * I[i-1] - nu * R[i-1] + (k1_t - k2_t
    + k3_t - k4_t) * N[i-1]
    dS_dt = mu * N[i-1] - nu * S[i-1] - beta * S[i-
    1] * I[i-1] / N[i-1] + (k1_t - k2_t + k3_t - k4_t)
    * N[i-1]

    # Updating values using the Euler method
    I[i] = I[i-1] + dt * dI_dt
    E[i] = E[i-1] + dt * dE_dt
    N[i] = N[i-1] + dt * dN_dt
    R[i] = R[i-1] + dt * dR_dt
    S[i] = S[i-1] + dt * dS_dt

# Plotting the results
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
plt.plot(t, S, label="S(t) - Susceptible")
plt.plot(t, E, label="E(t) - Exposed")
plt.plot(t, I, label="I(t) - Infected")
plt.plot(t, R, label="R(t) - Recovered")
plt.plot(t, N, label="N(t) - Population")
plt.xlabel("Time t")
plt.ylabel("Population")
plt.title("Epidemiological Model Simulation")
plt.legend()
plt.grid(True)
plt.show()

To run the following steps can be executed:
1. Copy the code and open a Python
environment such as Jupyter Notebook or a .py
file.

```

- The user must ensure that they have the numpy and matplotlib libraries installed. If not, they can be installed using the pip install numpy matplotlib command.
- Run the code to see the results of the epidemiological model simulation.

Figure 1. Graphical representation of the functions in the model (11)

The graph in figure (11) illustrates the dynamics of the different compartments:

- $S(t)$: Susceptible population decreases as individuals are exposed or infected.
- $E(t)$: The initially exposed population increases, indicating an increase in the number

of individuals who have been exposed but not yet infected.

- $I(t)$: The infected population shows increasing and decreasing trends, suggesting periods of active infection in the population.

- $R(t)$: The recovered population increases as infected individuals recover and acquire immunity.

- $N(t)$: The total population size, which fluctuates according to the time factors specified by the functions $k_1(t)$, $k_2(t)$, $k_3(t)$, $k_4(t)$.

Both the SIR model and its generalizations conclusively model the evolution of epidemics, which is why they have been used several times throughout human history to study the spread of different epidemics. The introduction of new compartments, in addition to that of the susceptible, the infected, the recovered, have often led to obtaining results with smaller errors.

The fractional derivative SIR model, and its generalizations rewritten with fractional derivatives, provide a more detailed and realistic representation of disease spread, taking into account the complex dynamics of interactions in the population and the memory effect. This model may be preferred in situations where epidemic behavior is more complex or when long-term effects are important. The classic SIR model remains useful for simpler cases or when a fast and direct approximation of the epidemic evolution is needed.

Figure 2. Comparison of Results for the SIR Model (left) and the SIR Model with Fractional Derivatives (right)

Table 1. Observations on the Example from the Figure 2

Classic <i>SIR</i> model	<i>SIR</i> model with fractional derivatives
The maximum number of infected individuals appears earlier, and then decreases as more and more individuals recover.	The response is more “delayed” and more gradual. The number of infected individuals reaches a peak later than the classic model.
The rate of change is more abrupt, which suggests a more deterministic and predictable behavior in the spread of the disease.	The fractional derivative brings a memory effect, which makes the spread and recovery slower and more extended over time.

For the case study with solutions represented in Figure 2, we consider a community of 1000 people, in which an infectious disease breaks out. At the beginning of the epidemic, 990 people are susceptible (S_0), 10 are infected (I_0), and 0 are recovered (R_0).

The following parameters were used:

- Rate of disease transmission: $\beta=0.3$
- Rate of recovery: $\gamma=0.1$
- Simulation period: 50 days

In order to analyze the spread of disease, we used both the classic *SIR* model, as well as the *SIR* model with fractional derivatives (with $\alpha = 0.9$).

For the classic *SIR* model, the equations are:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dS(t)}{dt} = -\beta S(t)I(t) \\ \frac{dI(t)}{dt} = \beta S(t)I(t) - \gamma I(t) \\ \frac{dR(t)}{dt} = \gamma I(t) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Functions S , I and R are time functions $S=S(t)$, $I=I(t)$, $R=R(t)$, differentiable on the interval $[0, \infty)$;

β -rate of transmission, is the parameter that controls the transfer between S and I . It

represents the average number of contacts needed per time unit to infect a person;

γ -is the transfer rate between I and R , and it represents their recovery rate. Then $1/\gamma$ shows the length of the time interval in which an individual becomes infected.

For the *SIR* model with Caputo fractional derivatives, the equations can be written as in the following example system:

$$\begin{cases} {}^{FF}D_{0,t}^\alpha S(t) = -\beta S(t)I(t) \\ {}^{FF}D_{0,t}^\alpha I(t) = \beta S(t)I(t) - \gamma I(t) \\ {}^{FF}D_{0,t}^\alpha R(t) = \gamma I(t) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

with initial conditions $S(0) \geq 0$, $I(0) \geq 0$ and $R(0) \geq 0$.

Definition 1. Let $0 \leq \alpha, \sigma \leq 1$. Then the fractional derivative and the fractional integral of a function g are described by the relations:

$${}^{FF}D_{0,t}^\alpha g(t) = \frac{d}{ds^\alpha} g(s) = \lim_{t \rightarrow s} \frac{g(t) - g(s)}{t^\alpha - s^\alpha},$$

$${}^{FF}J_{0,t}^{\sigma, \alpha}(g(t)) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\sigma)} \frac{d}{dt^\alpha} \int_0^t (t-s)^{m-\sigma-1} g(s) ds,$$

where Γ is gamma function, $\Gamma(p) = \int_0^\infty u^{p-1} e^{-u} du$, $p \in \mathbb{C} - \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}$, $\frac{1}{\Gamma(-k)} = 0$, $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$

In this model, $S(t)$ represents the number of susceptible individuals in a population at time t , $I(t)$ - the volume of infected individuals and $R(t)$ - the volume of recovered individuals. We assume that the parameters used in the model are positive. Therefore, $N(t) = S(t) + I(t) + R(t)$. In this model, the rate of susceptible individuals is represented by β , γ represents the transmission rate of the disease.

In the following we will also use other basic concepts regarding fractional operators:

Definition 2. Let $0 \leq \sigma, \sigma_1 \leq 1$. Then the fractional integral with exponential kernel is described by:

$${}^{FFE}J_{0,t}^{\sigma,\sigma_1}(g(t)) = \frac{M(\sigma)}{\Gamma(m-\sigma)} \frac{d}{dt^{\sigma_1}} \int_0^t \exp\left[-\frac{\sigma}{1-\sigma}(t-s)^{\nu-\sigma-1}\right] g(s) ds, \quad (14)$$

where $\sigma > 0$, $\sigma_1 \leq \nu \in N$ and $M(0) = M(1) = 1$.

$$M(\alpha) = \frac{2}{2-\alpha}, \alpha \in (0,2).$$

Definition 3. Let $0 \leq \sigma, \sigma_1 \leq 1$. Then the Mittag-Leffler generalized fractional integral is described by:

$${}^{FFM}J_{0,t}^{\sigma,\sigma_1}(g(t)) = \frac{AB(\sigma)}{1-\sigma} \frac{d}{dt^{\sigma_1}} \int_0^t E_{\sigma}\left[-\frac{\sigma}{1-\sigma}(t-s)^{\sigma}\right] g(s) ds, \quad (15)$$

where $\sigma > 0$, $\sigma_1 \leq 1$, and $AB(\sigma) = 1 - \sigma + \frac{\sigma}{\Gamma(\sigma)}$.

Definition 4. Let $0 \leq \sigma, \sigma_1 \leq 1$ and the real function g defined on the interval $[0, \infty)$. The fractional integral of g is described by:

$${}^{FFP}I_{0,t}^{\sigma,\sigma_1}(g(t)) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\sigma_1)} \int_0^t s^{1-\sigma_1}(t-s)^{\sigma-1} g(s) ds. \quad (16)$$

Definition 5. Let $0 \leq \sigma, \sigma_1 \leq 1$ and the real function g defined on the interval $[0, \infty)$. The fractional integral of g with exponential kernel is described

$${}^{FFE}I_{0,t}^{\sigma,\sigma_1}(g(t)) = \frac{\sigma_1(1-\sigma)t^{\sigma_1-1}g(t)}{M(\sigma)} + \frac{\sigma\sigma_1}{M(\sigma)} \int_0^t s^{\sigma-1} g(s) ds. \quad (17)$$

Definition 6. Let $0 \leq \sigma, \sigma_1 \leq 1$ and the real function g defined on the interval $[0, \infty)$. The fractional integral of g with a Mittag-Leffler kernel is described by:

$${}^{FFM}J_{0,t}^{\sigma,\sigma_1}(g(t)) = \frac{\sigma_1(1-\sigma)t^{\sigma_1-1}g(t)}{AB(\sigma)} + \frac{\sigma\sigma_1}{AB(\sigma)} \int_0^t s^{\sigma-1}(t-s)g(s) ds. \quad (18)$$

The two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function has the formula:

$$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + \beta)}, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) > 0, \beta \in \mathbb{C},$$

where Γ is gamma function,

$$\Gamma(p) = \int_0^{\infty} u^{p-1} e^{-u} du, p \in \mathbb{C} - \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}, \frac{1}{\Gamma(-k)} = 0, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

It is the generalization of the function written for one parameter:

$$E_{\alpha}(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(\alpha n + 1)}, \operatorname{Re}(\alpha) \exp(z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n!} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{\Gamma(n+1)}. \quad (19)$$

The equilibrium points for model (13) can be of two types, namely disease-free equilibrium and endemic equilibrium. We assume that E' represents the disease-free equilibrium and the endemic equilibrium is represented by E^* . We have

$$E' = (S', I', R') = (0, 0, N),$$

$$S^* = \frac{N}{\beta I^*}, \quad I^* = \frac{S^*}{N - \gamma S^* - \beta R^*}.$$

The reproduction number R_0 , given by the formula, is also obtained $R_0 = \frac{\beta S(0)}{N\gamma}$.

Existence of the Solution of the System (13)

We make the notations $C(t, S, I, R) = -\beta S(t)I(t)$, $D(t, S, I, R) = \beta S(t)I(t) - \gamma I(t)$, $E(t, S, I, R) = \gamma I(t)$,

$$\Pi(t) = (S(t), I(t), R(t)),$$

$$\Pi(0) = (S(0), I(0), R(0)).$$

The system (13) become:

$$\begin{cases} {}^{FF}D_t^\alpha \Pi(t) = \alpha t^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) \\ \Pi(0) = \Pi_0 \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Applying the fractional derivative, one finds:

$$\Pi(t) = \Pi(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1(1-\sigma)}}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau,$$

Where

$$\Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) = \begin{cases} C(t, S, I, R) \\ D(t, S, I, R) \\ E(t, S, I, R) \end{cases}$$

We choose the Banach space $B = C \times C \times C \times C$, where $C = [0, T]$ with the norm

$$\|\Pi\| = \max_{t \in [0, T]} |S(t) + I(t) + R(t)|$$

We define the operator $\mathfrak{N}: B \rightarrow B$ by the following formula:

$$\mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t) = \Pi(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1(1-\sigma)}}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau. \quad (21)$$

We suppose that:

For each $\Pi \in B$, \exists the constants $C_\Lambda > 0$ and M_Λ such that

$$|\Lambda(t, \Pi(t))| \leq C_\Lambda |\Pi(t)| + M_\Lambda. \quad (22)$$

We suppose that $\Pi, \bar{\Pi} \in B$ and \exists a constant $L_\Lambda > 0$ such that

$$|\Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) - \Lambda(t, \bar{\Pi}(t))| \leq L_\Lambda |\Pi(t) - \bar{\Pi}(t)|. \quad (23)$$

Theorem 5. *If the condition (23) take place, let $\Lambda: [0, T] \times B \rightarrow R$ be a continuous function. Then, exists the solution of the system (20).*

Proof. Λ and \mathfrak{N} are continuous operators.

We suppose that $H = \{\Pi \in B: \|\Pi\| \leq R, R > 0\}$. For all $\Pi \in B$, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathfrak{N}(\Pi)| &= \max_{t \in [0, T]} \left| \Pi(0) + \frac{t^{\alpha-1(1-\sigma)}}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau \right| \leq \\ &\Pi(0) + \frac{\alpha T^{\alpha-1(1-\sigma)}}{AB(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda \|\Pi\| + M_\Lambda) + \\ &\max_{t \in [0, T]} \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \Pi(0) + \frac{\sigma_1 T^{\alpha-1(1-\sigma)}}{AB(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda \|\Pi\| + M_\Lambda) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda \|\Pi\| + M_\Lambda) T^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha) \leq R.$$

Thus:

$$|\mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t_2) - \mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t_1)| = \left| \frac{\alpha t_2^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t_2, \Pi(t_2)) + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^{t_2} \tau^{\alpha-1} (t_2 - \tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau - \frac{\alpha t_1^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t_1, \Pi(t_1)) + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^{t_1} \tau^{\alpha-1} (t_1 - \tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau \right|$$

$$\leq \left| \frac{\alpha t_2^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda |\Pi(t)| + M_\Lambda) + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda |\Pi(t)| + M_\Lambda) t_2^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha) - \frac{\alpha t_1^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda |\Pi(t)| + M_\Lambda) + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda |\Pi(t)| + M_\Lambda) t_1^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha) \right|.$$

For $t_1 \rightarrow t_2$ we have $|\mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t_2) - \mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t_1)| \rightarrow 0$. Then $\|\mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t_2) - \mathfrak{N}(\Pi)(t_1)\| \rightarrow 0$, for $t_1 \rightarrow t_2$.

Thus, \mathfrak{N} is an equicontinuous operator. We applied the Schauder theorem from the fixed point theory, and we obtained the conclusion of our Theorem 6.

Theorem 6. *If the condition (23) take place and $\rho < 1$, where*

$$\rho = \left(\frac{\alpha T^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda \|\Pi\| + M_\Lambda) T^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha) \right) L_A,$$

Then the system (20) have a unique solution.

Proof. For each $\Pi, \bar{\Pi} \in B$, the following relation take place:

$$|\mathfrak{N}(\Pi) - \mathfrak{N}(\bar{\Pi})| = \max_{t \in [0, T]} \left| \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} (\Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) - \Lambda(t, \bar{\Pi}(t))) + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t - \tau)^{\alpha-1} d\tau (\Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) - \Lambda(\tau, \bar{\Pi}(\tau))) \right|$$

$$\Lambda(\tau, \bar{\Pi}(\tau)) \leq \left[\frac{\alpha T^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} + \frac{\sigma\alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} (C_\Lambda \|\Pi\| M_\Lambda) T^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha) \right] \|\Pi - \bar{\Pi}\| \leq \rho \|\Pi - \bar{\Pi}\|$$

Thus, \mathfrak{N} is a contraction. Based on Banach's contraction principle, results that the solution of the system (20) is unique.

$$\begin{aligned} T_1(S(t), I(t), R(t)) &= S(t) - {}^{ABR}D_0^\sigma S(t) + \alpha t^{\alpha-1} C(t, S, I, R), \\ T_2(S(t), I(t), R(t)) &= I(t) - {}^{FF}D_{0,t}^\alpha I(t) + \alpha t^{\alpha-1} D(t, S, I, R), \end{aligned}$$

$$T_3(S(t), I(t), R(t)) = R(t) - {}^{FF}D_{0,t}^\alpha R(t) + \alpha t^{\alpha-1} E(t, S, I, R).$$

Let $Pcl(R)$ the set of the nonempty and closed subsets of R .

Theorem 7. (Frenk & Schaible, 2004) *Let $A \in M_{m,m}(R_+)$. The following properties are equivalents:*

- (i) A converges to zero;
- (ii) $A^n \rightarrow 0$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$;
- (iii) Each absolute value for eigenvalues of the matrix A is less then 1;
- (iv) The matrix $I - A$ is inversable, with $(I - A)^{-1} = I + A + \dots + A^n + \dots$.

We established the following theorem for the case in which $T_i: R \rightarrow Pcl(R)$ for $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ are contractions. For example, for the case in which the absolute values of the derivatives are less then 1. This situation take place for example the variations of the function $S = S(t), I = I(t), R = R(t)$ are small.

Theorem 8. *Let $T_i: R \rightarrow Pcl(R)$ with $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$ be the contractions and $0 \leq a_{kk} \leq 1, k \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. Let $(S(t_1), I(t_1), R(t_1)), (S(t_2), I(t_2), R(t_2)) \in R^3$ where t_1 and t_2 are moments of time from the interval J . For each $y_k = T_k(S(t_1), I(t_1), R(t_1)), k \in$*

$\{1,2,3\}$ exists $z_k = T_k(S(t_1), I(t_1), R(t_1))$ such that for all $k \in \{1,2,3\}$:

$$|y_k - z_k| \leq a_{11}|S(t_2) - S(t_1)|,$$

$$|y_k - z_k| \leq a_{22}|I(t_2) - I(t_1)|,$$

$$|y_k - z_k| \leq a_{33}|R(t_2) - R(t_1)|.$$

Then the system:

$$\begin{cases} S(t) \in T_1(S(t), I(t), R(t)) \\ I(t) \in T_2(S(t), I(t), R(t)) \\ R(t) \in T_3(S(t), I(t), R(t)) \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

has at least one solution in R^3 .

Proof. The theorem in a particular case of the Theorem 3.1 from an article of the authors Bucur et al., 2009.

Ulam-Hyers Stability

Definition 7. The system (20) is Ulam-Hyers stable, if $\exists \mathfrak{K}_{\sigma, \alpha} \geq 0$ such that for all $\varepsilon > 0$ and for all $\Pi \in (C[0, T], R)$ the following inequality take place $|{}^{FF}D_t^{\sigma, \alpha} \Pi(t) - \Lambda(t, \Pi(t))| \leq \varepsilon, t \in [0, T]$

and exists a unique solution $\Omega \in (C[0, T], R)$ such that

$$|\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)| \leq \mathfrak{K}_{\sigma, \alpha} \varepsilon, t \in [0, T]; \Phi(t) \leq \varepsilon \text{ for } \varepsilon > 0; {}^{FF}D_t^{\sigma, \alpha} \Pi(t) = \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \Phi(t).$$

Lemma 1. The perturbed solution of the system (20), satisfy the inequality

$$\left| \mathfrak{K}(t) - \left(\Pi(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau \right) \right| \leq \sigma_{\sigma, \alpha}^* \varepsilon, \quad (25)$$

$$\sigma_{\sigma, \alpha}^* = \frac{\alpha T^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} T^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha).$$

Proof. Analogous with Farman et. al.2024.

Lemma 2. The solution of the system (20) is Ulam-Hyers stable, if $\rho < 1$, in the conditions of the lemma 1.

Proof. We suppose that $\Omega \in B$ is the unique solution and $\Pi \in B$ is a perturbed solution. We have

$$|\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)| = \left| \Pi(t) - \left(\Omega(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Omega(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Omega(\tau)) d\tau \right) \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \Pi(t) - \left(\Pi(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau \right) \right| + \\ & \left| \Pi(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Pi(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Pi(\tau)) d\tau \right| - \\ & \left| \Omega(0) + \frac{\alpha t^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} \Lambda(t, \Omega(t)) + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} \int_0^t \tau^{\alpha-1} (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} \Lambda(\tau, \Omega(\tau)) d\tau \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \leq \sigma_{\sigma, \alpha}^* \varepsilon + \left(\frac{\sigma_1 T^{\alpha-1}(1-\sigma)}{AB(\sigma)} + \frac{\sigma \alpha}{AB(\sigma)\Gamma(\sigma)} T^{\sigma+\alpha-1} R(\sigma, \alpha) \right) L_{\Lambda} |\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)| \\ & \leq \sigma_{\sigma, \alpha}^* \varepsilon + \rho |\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)|. \end{aligned}$$

Then

$$\|\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)\| \leq \sigma_{\sigma, \alpha}^* \varepsilon + \rho \|\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)\|$$

From the last relation we obtained

$$\|\Pi(t) - \Omega(t)\| \leq \aleph_{\sigma, \alpha} \varepsilon,$$

where $\aleph_{\sigma, \alpha} = \frac{\sigma^* \alpha}{1 - \rho}$. Then the system is stable.

Simulations

In this section we present a set of fractional programming problems solved in GeoGebra, Maple and MATLAB.

How to Use GeoGebra software?

Example 1. Solve the following linear problem using the GeoGebra program:

$$\begin{cases} \min \left(\frac{3}{xy} \right) \\ x + 2y \leq 8 \\ 2x + y \leq 6 \\ x > 0, y > 0 \end{cases}$$

The objective function is $f(x, y) = \frac{3}{xy}$ and the solution is $f(K) = \frac{3}{1.33 \times 3.33} \cong 0.677$ (Fig.3).

Figure 3. The Solution of the Example 1, in GeoGebra

We have $f(I) = 1/2 (0+1) \cdot 5 = -4,5$, $f(J) = 0$, $f(K) = 1/2(16-0) \cdot 16 = -8$, $f(L) = 1/2(9+4) \cdot 12 \cdot 10 = -15,5$, which implies that $f_{\min} = -15,5$.

How to Use Maple Software?

Example 2.

$$\begin{cases} \max \frac{x_2 - 2}{(x_1 - 1)^2 + (x_2 - 1)^2 + 1} \\ x_1 \geq 0, x_2 \geq 0 \end{cases}$$

Figure 4. The Solution of the Example 2, in Maple

As seen in Figure 4, and as expected for concave-convex functions, there is only one maximum point and one minimum point, which are actually global optimum points. The fact that the function in Example 2 is concave-convex is verified by the fact that a function that is convex has the Hessian matrix positive semidefinite. And concave functions are opposite to convex functions.

We introduced a constraint in Example 2 with a restriction $x_1 + x_2 \leq 100$, we used NLPsolve command in Maple and we can calculate the maximum of the objective function equal to the number 0.207106781186547518:

```
with(Optimization);
```

```
CS := {x[1] + x[2] ≤ 100};
```

```
f := (x[2] - 2) / ((x[1] - 1)^2 + (x[2] - 1)^2 + 1);
```

```
[ImportMPS, Interactive, LPSolve, LSSolve, Maximize, Minimize, NLPsolve, QPSolve]
```

$$\{x_1 + x_2 \leq 100\}$$

$$\frac{x_2 - 2}{(x_1 - 1)^2 + (x_2 - 1)^2 + 1}$$

Figure 5. We Introduced the Problem in Maple


```
NLPsolve(= CS, assume = nonnegative, maximize);
```

```
[0.207106781186547518, [x1 = 1., x2 = 3.41421356231120]]
```

Figure 5. Graphic Representation of the Objective Function and the Solution in Maple

For some specific types of fractional problems (e.g., linear fractional problems), it is possible to directly apply the Frank-Wolfe method by iteratively solving a linear approximation of the objective function.

The Frank-Wolfe method is suitable for solving convex optimization problems of the form $\min_{x \in S} h(x)$, where $h(x)$ is a convex function, and S is a convex feasible region. The method involves iteratively moving towards an optimal solution by solving a linear approximation of the objective function at each iteration.

Steps in the Frank-Wolfe Method for Fractional Programming, are:

Initialization: Start with an initial feasible solution $x_0 \in S$.

Linearization: At each iteration k , linearize the objective function around the current point x_k : $\nabla h(x_k)^T (x - x_k)$

Subproblem Solution: Solve the linear subproblem: $s_k = \operatorname{argmin}_{x \in S} \nabla h(x_k)^T x$.

Update: Move towards the solution of the subproblem: $x_{k+1} = x_k + \gamma_k (s_k - x_k)$,

where γ_k is a step size that can be determined through line search or a fixed schedule.

Convergence Check: Repeat the process until the solution converges to a predefined tolerance.

For the applying in a maximum problem, it's known that $\max(b) = -\min(-b)$. Hence, the role of b is substitute with $-b$ in the above algorithm.

Example 3. A Case Study: Optimizing Vaccination Rates Between Regions

Context. A city is divided into two regions (Region A and Region B), and authorities aim to optimize the vaccination rate to minimize the combined infection rate. However, the vaccination costs vary between regions, and the total budget is limited.

The goal is to maximize the ratio between vaccination effectiveness and total costs.

Model.

Let:

x_1 : the percentage of the population vaccinated in Region A;

x_2 : the percentage of the population vaccinated in Region B.

The objective function is given as a fractional ratio:

$$h(x_1, x_2) = \frac{\ln(1+x_1)+\ln(1+2x_2)}{c_1x_1+c_2x_2+1}$$

where:

$c_1 = 5$: cost of vaccinating one person in Region A,

$c_2 = 3$: cost of vaccinating one person in Region B.

Goal: Maximize $h(x_1, x_2)$.

Constraints:

-total available budget: $c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 \leq 12$,

-the vaccination rate must be positive and not exceed 100%: $0 \leq x_1, x_2 \leq 1$.

The fractional problem can be reformulated into an equivalent nonlinear problem, such as:

$$\max z(x_1, x_2) = \ln(1 + x_1) + \ln(1 + 2x_2) - \lambda(c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 + 1)$$

where λ is updated iteratively until $\lambda = h(x_1, x_2)$.

Solving Numerically Using the Frank-Wolfe Method.
The Frank-Wolfe method is used to solve nonlinear optimization problems with linear constraints. The Maple implementation, is:

restart;

with(Optimization):

Parameters of the problem

$c_1 := 5$: # Cost per person in Region A

$c_2 := 3$: # Cost per person in Region B

budget := 12: # Total budget

Fractional function (for reference)

$$h := (x_1, x_2) \rightarrow (\ln(1 + x_1) + \ln(1 + 2x_2)) / (c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 + 1):$$

Reformulating the fractional function (with lambda)

lambda := 0: # Initializing lambda

$$z := (x_1, x_2, lambda) \rightarrow \ln(1 + x_1) + \ln(1 + 2x_2) - lambda*(c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 + 1):$$

Constraints

$$\text{constraints} := [c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 \leq \text{budget}, 0 \leq x_1, x_1 \leq 1, 0 \leq x_2, x_2 \leq 1]:$$

Initial parameters

tol := 1e-5: # Tolerance

max_iter := 100: # Maximum number of iterations

x_k := [0, 0]: # Initial solution

Frank-Wolfe Algorithm for optimizing g

for k from 1 to max_iter do

 # Gradient of g at the current point

$$\text{grad} := [\text{diff}(z(x_1, x_2, \text{lambda}), x_1), \text{diff}(z(x_1, x_2, \text{lambda}), x_2)]:$$

$$\text{grad} := \text{eval}(\text{grad}, [x_1 = x_k[1], x_2 = x_k[2]]):$$

 # Linear problem to find the direction

 dir_problem := Optimization[Minimize](

$$\text{grad}[1]*x_1 + \text{grad}[2]*x_2,$$

 constraints,

$$\text{variables} = [x_1, x_2]$$

):

 d_k := dir_problem[2] - Vector(x_k): # Direction of movement

 # Optimal step size

```
gamma := fsolve(diff(z(x_k[1] + t*d_k[1],
x_k[2] + t*d_k[2], lambda), t) = 0, t, 0..1);
```

```
# Update the solution
```

```
x_k := x_k + gamma * d_k;
```

```
# Update lambda
```

```
lambda := eval(f(x_k[1], x_k[2]));
```

```
# Check tolerance
```

```
if Norm(d_k) < tol then
```

```
    break;
```

```
end if;
```

```
end do;
```

```
# Final result
```

```
x_k, eval(f(x_k[1], x_k[2]));
```

Expected results are:

- vector x_k : contains the optimal vaccination rates for each region;
- value $h(x_1, x_2)$: represents the maximized value of the fractional objective function.

This implementation can be adapted for other similar problems.

How to Use MATLAB Software?

Example 4.

For a fractional optimization problem with the following form:

$$\begin{cases} \max \left(\frac{c^T x}{d^T x} \right) \\ Ax \leq b \\ x \geq 0 \end{cases},$$

We can apply the Charnes-Cooper transform and we will replace this problem into a linear

programming problem. The second problem, equivalent with the first problem, can be solved, for examples, with MATLAB software, if we use the following code:

```
function [x_opt, fval_opt] =
solve_fractional_programming(c, d, A, b)

% solve_fractional_programming – Solves
the fractional programming problem
% max (c^T x) / (d^T x)
% subject to: A x <= b, x >= 0
%
% Inputs:
% c – Coefficient vector for the numerator in
the objective function
% d – Coefficient vector for the denominator
in the objective function
% A – Coefficient matrix for the inequality
constraints
% b – Right-hand side vector for the
inequality constraints
%
% Outputs:
% x_opt – Optimal solution vector
% fval_opt – Optimal value of the objective
function

% Get the number of variables
n = length(c);

% Transformation variables
f = [zeros(n, 1); 1]; % Objective function for
LP
Aeq = [d', -1]; % Equality constraint for LP
beq = 1; % Right-hand side for equality
constraint

% Augment the original A matrix and b vector
to include the new variable
```

```

A_new = [A, zeros(size(A, 1), 1)];
lb = zeros(n+1, 1); % Lower bounds (x >= 0
and new variable t >= 0)

% Solve the linear programming problem
options = optimoptions('linprog', 'Display',
'off');
[z, fval] = linprog(f, A_new, b, Aeq, beq, lb,
[], [], options);

% Extract the optimal solution
x_opt = z(1:n) / z(end); % Normalize by the
last element
fval_opt = c' * x_opt / (d' * x_opt); %
Optimal value of the original fractional objective

fprintf('Optimal solution: \n');
disp(x_opt);
fprintf('Optimal value of the objective
function: \n');
disp(fval_opt);
end

% Example usage:
c = [3; 5];
d = [1; 2];
A = [1, 2; 2, 1];
b = [4; 3];

```

```

[x_opt, fval_opt] =
solve_fractional_programming(c, d, A, b);

```

Function: 'solve_fractional_programming'
receives the coefficient vectors 'c' and 'd' for the
objective functions and the matrices 'A' and 'b'
for the constraints.

Charnes-Cooper Transformation:

- Constructs a new coefficient vector 'f' for the linear programming problem, which includes the additional variable 't'.
- Defines an equality constraint 'Aeq' and 'beq' to ensure that 'd' * x = 1' (normalization).
- Augments the matrix 'A' and vector 'b' to include the additional variable.

Solving the Linear Programming Problem:

- Uses the 'linprog' function to solve the equivalent linear programming problem.
- Extracts the optimal solution and normalizes it to obtain the original solution 'x_opt'.

Example Usage: The code includes an example with values for 'c', 'd', 'A', and 'b' to demonstrate how to use the function.

Conclusion

Fractional programming problems, one of the topics of mathematical optimization that has many applications in the field of economics, life sciences, like other types of mathematical optimization, can be solved quite quickly in various software, such as GeoGebra, Maple and MATLAB software. The use of simulations, for example, in these computer programs, can increase the quality of the teaching-learning process for students, in subjects such as Operational Research or Optimization Techniques. In this work we presented numerical examples to illustrate the methodology and the efficiency of some software in solving linear and nonlinear fractional programming problems.

Fractional programming is a vital area of optimization with significant theoretical and practical importance. The continuous development of more sophisticated algorithms and computational techniques promises to extend its applicability to new and emerging fields. Future research directions include the integration of machine learning methods to enhance the solution process and the exploration of real-time applications in dynamic and uncertain environments.

The case study demonstrates the application of the Frank-Wolfe method to a linear fractional programming problem in the context of a practical problem from the life sciences.

Epidemiological models or pollution models, can provide particular cases of numerators and denominators for objective functions in fractional programming problems. And in the case when they are written with fractional derivatives, they are more refined.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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